

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: broiler

Level: husbandry

Keywords: behaviour, health and body condition, management, mutilation

Background context provided by the requestor

This query concerns cannibalism, the causative factors and management in free range broiler systems (slaughtered at 56 days + old).

Question raised by the requestor

Causative factors in a cannibalism outbreak in broiler flocks, including free-range flocks. How significant is nutrition, feed quantity, feeding frequency, lighting regime, and genetics (fast versus slow growing bird genotypes)?

Answer

Cannibalism in poultry production refers to forms of injurious pecking that involve pecks to the skin, vent, or toes (Rodenburg et al., 2013). Cannibalistic pecking can eventually lead to the victim's death through blood loss and tissue damage (Rodenburg et al., 2013). This behaviour can be an escalation of severe feather pecking (SFP) behaviour which creates damage to the plumage through the forceful removal of feathers (Cronin & Glatz, 2020). These featherless areas can then become targets for cannibalistic pecking, resulting in open wounds (Leishman et al., 2022).

This problem is predominant in poultry species or categories with longer production cycles (i.e., laying hens, turkeys), and is therefore less common in conventional broiler flocks that have commonly shorter lifespan. For example, in laying hens, severe feather pecking can occur anytime during the rearing period but often increases as hens reach sexual maturity (EFSA, 2023). As such, there is a lack of literature on cannibalism in broiler flocks, although this is a growing area of interest due to the increased use of slower-growing broiler genotypes that live longer in alternative systems, whereas fast-growing genotypes are usually slaughtered before reaching sexual maturity.

In this query, we review the broiler literature on the topic when available. Otherwise, we assume the causative mechanisms for cannibalism are the same across poultry species, and we will therefore briefly review findings from species such as turkeys and finding from laying hens. Across poultry species, numerous factors have been implicated as causative factors for cannibalism and/or injurious pecking. Broadly, these can be grouped into bird, husbandry, and nutritional factors.

Bird Factors

Behaviour. In broiler chickens, death from cannibalism is typically due to vent pecking (i.e., pecks aimed at the cloacal region) (Nielsen et al., 2003). However, wounds in the skin caused by other forms of injurious pecking (i.e., SFP) can also induce or escalate in cannibalistic behaviours. Forceful removal of feathers via SFP can cause bleeding of the follicle or skin, triggering cannibalistic pecking (McAdie & Keeling, 2000). Studies of free-range laying hens have shown that the risk of flocks showing cannibalism increases with the rate of SFP (Lambton et al., 2023). In fact, McAdie and Keeling (2000) found that artificially damaging the feather cover (without damaging the skin) in their experimental treatments

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resulted in cannibalism outbreaks in half of the experimental groups, and that cannibalistic attacks were initiated in these feather-damaged areas, especially near the rump. Therefore, while causative factors for SFP may not cause cannibalism *per se*, the display of SFP may increase the risk of cannibalism also occurring. SFP is hypothesised to be a form of redirected pecking or foraging behaviour which can arise when birds are lacking the opportunity to express these motivated behaviours (van Staaveren & Harlander, 2020). Indeed, laying hen flocks that exhibit more foraging behaviour have been shown to be less likely to display SFP (Gilani et al., 2012). These types of pecking behaviours have been shown to be socially transmissible, and this has been demonstrated in a study of caged laying hens (Tablante et al., 2000) which demonstrated that the occurrence of cannibalism was not random but distributed in clusters.

Genetics. Some genotypes of poultry may have a higher likelihood of displaying cannibalistic behaviours. Studies of broilers (Nielsen et al., 2003) and free-range laying hens (Kjaer & Sørensen, 2002) have noted differences in mortality from cannibalism between genotypes, indicating some contribution of genetics to the development of this behaviour. Moreover, selection experiments have been able to produce hybrids which differ in their likelihood of mortality from cannibalism (Cheng & Muir, 2007). In turkeys, differences in the prevalence of pecking injuries have been reported between genotypes where lighter genotypes show fewer injuries (Haug et al., 2023; Olschewsky, 2019).

Some studies have demonstrated that cannibalism and SFP are heritable for laying hens which allow a potential for breeding programs to select against these behavioural expressions (Bennewitz et al., 2014; Craig & Muir, 1993; Kjaer & Sørensen, 1997). The genetic component of feather pecking has been further supported by selective breeding experiments resulting in hybrids that differ significantly in their expression of SFP (Kjaer et al., 2001). However, assessment of heritability for cannibalism or SFP have yet to be investigated for broiler chickens.

Husbandry Factors (Environment and Management)

There are several factors related to the environmental and management conditions that have been associated with increased risk of injurious pecking in poultry. Generally, unfavourable conditions that do not meet the needs of the birds increase the risk of development of injurious pecking behaviour (Cronin & Glatz, 2020).

Stocking density. High stocking densities have been associated with increased feather pecking and cannibalism in turkeys (Beaulac & Schwan-Lardner, 2018; Buchwalder & Huber-Eicher, 2004; Ellerbrock, 2000; Jhetam et al., 2022) and layer pullets (EFSA, 2023). However, other studies report no effect (Martrenchar et al., 1999). High stocking densities may limit exploratory behaviour, thus resulting in redirected pecking (EFSA, 2023). In broiler chickens (mix of Ross 500 and 508), high (40 kg/m²) stocking densities resulted in a decrease in locomotion and ground pecking compared to the lower density treatment (34 kg/m²) (Hall, 2001). Similar results were found by other studies of broiler chickens showing a decrease in exploratory behaviours with increasing stocking density (Blokhuys & Van der Haar, 1990).

Temperature, Lighting, and Noise. In turkeys, it has been reported that young birds increase their frequency of scratching, shivering, and cannibalism when exposed to low temperatures and high humidity (Mendes et al., 2020). For birds reared in free-range or organic systems, this aspect may be more difficult to manage in the outdoor environment. However, sufficient shelters or access to appropriate indoor environments could be provided to help mitigate these effects.

In terms of lighting, broilers have been reported to exhibit less feather-pecking behaviour in Osram 830 warm-white fluorescent light compared to Osram Biolux 965 fluorescent light (with similar colour temperature (6500 K) to daylight) and more foraging behaviour in dim rather than bright light intensities (Kristensen et al., 2007). High light intensities have been associated with increased risk of injurious pecking in laying hens (Drake et al., 2010). Related to this, access

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to covered verandas in regions with high light intensity may be associated with increased risk of feather pecking if opportunities to seek shade or darkness are not provided (EFSA, 2023).

It has been reported that acute exposure (10 min) to 80 or 100 decibel sounds significantly increases the plasma corticosterone concentrations of broiler chickens (Chloupek et al., 2009), which could potentially be interpreted as an indicator of stress. In addition to high sound levels, a high variability in sound can also influence injurious pecking. Gilani et al. (Gilani et al., 2012) found that the likelihood of SFP in laying hen flocks was higher when pullets had been reared in an environment with high sound variability.

Air quality. Poor air quality can increase the risk of injurious pecking in laying hens (Drake et al., 2010). Air quality problems can range from high levels of CO₂, ammonia, dust, or airborne pathogens and microorganisms. Bestman et al. (2009) found that high air ammonia level during the laying period was related to the level of feather damage, and other studies have associated higher ammonia levels with earlier onset of SFP (Drake et al., 2010). In a risk factor analysis, Drake et al. (2010) also found that elevated CO₂ levels between 24 – 30 weeks of age were associated with earlier onset of SFP. Specifically, they found that each increase of 200 ppm CO₂ (observed range: 43 – 2000 ppm) resulted in a 15% earlier onset of a mean flock feather score of >3.8 based on the system by Bright et al. (2006). In the Bright et al. (2006) system, a score of 4 is the worst possible score indicating severe damage to feathers, naked body areas greater than 5 cm², and haemorrhage/open skin. The results of Decina et al. (2019) further support air quality as an influential factor for development of SFP due to the association between infrequent running of the manure belt (increased likelihood of higher ammonia levels in the air) and higher incidence of feather damage.

Nutritional Factors

If dietary requirements are not met, foraging behaviour may be redirected to SFP. The interaction between nutrition and SFP has been reviewed in more depth elsewhere for domestic fowl (Kjaer & Bessei, 2013) and laying hens (M. Van Krimpen et al., 2005).

Feed form. In laying hens, presenting feed in a pelleted form and in combination with lack of litter, birds are more likely to redirect their foraging behaviour towards conspecifics, i.e. perform SFP (EFSA, 2023). This effect has also been seen in turkeys, where birds fed mash or crumble diets perform SFP less than those fed pellets (Hale & Schein, 1962; Hamilton & Kennie, 1997). One hypothesis about this relationship is that looser feed forms (i.e., mash or crumble) require longer feeding times compared to pellets, resulting in improved satisfaction of the motivation to perform foraging behaviour (Desbruslais et al., 2021).

Feed frequency and changes. In broiler breeders, feed restriction is a common management practice (aimed at maintaining health and reproductive competence in fast-growing broiler strains), but it raises major welfare concerns. Several studies have shown that feed-restricted broiler breeders display behaviours indicative of frustration, boredom, and hunger, such as stereotypic object pecking or increased aggressive pecking caused by feeding competition (De Jong & Guemene, 2011; Mench, 2002). Yet, redirected pecking is known to be related to SFP, which may lead to cannibalism (van Staaveren & Harlander, 2020). Also, in turkeys, injuries resulting from SFP have been reported to occur more frequently in feed-restricted birds compared to birds fed ad libitum (Hamilton & Kennie, 1997). Similarly, “skip-a-day” fed (fed two times a daily ration every other day) broiler breeder pullets performed more SFP compared to precision fed (fed multiple small meals daily via an automated system based on their current and target body weight) (Girard et al., 2017). Frequent dietary changes can be considered stressful. Some studies of laying hens report that the odds of SFP are higher in flocks with more dietary changes during the rearing period (Gilani et al., 2012).

Feed ingredients. Studies have shown that dietary deficiencies in domestic fowl, even without feed restriction, may increase feather pecking behaviour and cannibalism (Kjaer & Bessei, 2013; Van Krimpen et al., 2005). Increased

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injurious pecking behaviour has been associated with a deficiency in the diet of crude protein or specific amino acids (i.e., methionine) (Van Krimpen et al., 2005). Laying hens fed an organic diet low in protein and amino acids (135 g/kg crude protein, 5.9 g/kg lysine and 5.1 g/kg methionine + cysteine) experienced a higher incidence of pecking injuries in comparison with a standard organic diet (169 g/kg CP, 8.7 g/kg lysine and 6.7 g/kg methionine + cysteine) (Elwinger et al., 2002). Growing bantams (miniature chicken breed) (4 and 6 weeks old) fed tryptophan supplements at doses up to 22.6 g/kg reduced pecking damage compared to the control dose (2.6 g/kg) (Savory, 1998; Savory et al., 1999).

In addition to protein, low dietary fibre content has been associated with the development of SFP and cannibalism (reviewed in Desbruslais et al. (2021)). Briefly, low fibre diets have been linked to higher incidence of SFP and feather/skin damage compared to diets with a higher fibre content (Bearse et al., 1940; Steinfeldt et al., 2007). It is believed that higher fibre diets, or diets with lower nutrient density (Qaisrani et al., 2013), result in the birds spending more time foraging, and consequently the risk of redirection of foraging behaviour into SFP is reduced. However, some studies report different or no effects on SFP depending on the type of fibre they are using (soluble vs. insoluble) (Van Krimpen et al., 2009).

Conclusions

The development of cannibalism is associated with numerous causative factors. As cannibalism is closely linked to SFP, many of the causative factors are assumed to be shared between the two behaviours. Some bird-level causative factors are related to behaviours performed by the birds (i.e., SFP) as well as genetic line. Environmentally, high stocking density, loud/variable noise levels, and poor air quality may also contribute to the occurrence of pecking behaviours. Nutritionally, diets that are nutritionally deficient (i.e., too low in protein/amino acids) and/or not fed in sufficient quantities (i.e., restricted feeding) may cause SFP or cannibalism. The development of SFP and cannibalism is multifactorial but, generally speaking, causative factors predominantly include unfavourable conditions that result in physical or mental stress to the birds, resulting in more SFP and/or cannibalism. Overall, there is a lack of literature on the causative factors of cannibalism in broiler chickens, as the occurrence of this behaviour is relatively rare in these birds, particularly for fast-growing genotypes that are slaughtered before reaching sexual maturity.

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